

Issues for irrigation water management and soil salinity within a southern Tunisia oasis

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ABSTRACT

The oasis and arid zones of the Maghreb are facing major changes related to the modes of governance of water resources, climate change and the dynamics of agrarian systems. When it comes to cash crops such as the date palm in southern Tunisia, farmers tend to provide excessive volumes of water. In this context, poor irrigation management has led to a rise in the surface water table and a phenomenon of hydromorphy threatening the sustainability of the oasis system. The current study presents and discusses the issues for irrigation water management and soil salinity in date palms oasis in southern Tunisia. Farming practices were examined through surveys and participatory workshops with farmers. Also, continuous monitoring of soil water content and salinity was carried out on an agricultural plot using improved surface irrigation. The results show that there have been an excessive irrigations that are largely due to the lack of awareness of farmers of the date palm water needs. Analysis of the saline profiles of the studied plots showed an increase in vertical (intra-profile) and spatial (inter-profile) variability in relation to irrigation frequencies and sand amendment practices, salinity and groundwater depth. The sand amendment technique shows efficiency in the reduction of salinity provided to improve the drainage network and the awareness of farmers of better irrigation management according crop water requirements.

Keywords : Agricultural practices, oasis, irrigation water, salinity profiles.

RESUME

Problèmes de gestion de l'eau d'irrigation et de salinité du sol au sein d'une oasis du sud Tunisien

Les oasis et les zones arides du Maghreb font face à des changements majeurs liés aux modes de gouvernance des ressources en eau, aux changements climatiques et aux dynamiques des systèmes agraires. En ce qui concerne les cultures commerciales telles que le palmier-dattier dans le sud de la Tunisie, les agriculteurs ont tendance à fournir des volumes d'eau excessifs. Dans ce contexte, une mauvaise gestion de l'irrigation a entraîné une hausse de la nappe phréatique et un phénomène d'hydromorphie menaçant la durabilité du système oasien. L'étude actuelle présente et discute des problèmes de gestion de l'eau d'irrigation et de la salinité du sol dans les oasis de palmiers-dattiers du sud Tunisien. Les pratiques agricoles

ont été examinées à travers des enquêtes et des ateliers participatifs avec les agriculteurs. De plus, un suivi continu de la teneur en eau et de la salinité du sol a été réalisé sur des parcelles agricoles utilisant une irrigation de surface améliorée. Les résultats montrent qu'il y a eu des irrigations excessives dues au manque de sensibilisation des agriculteurs aux besoins en eau du palmier-dattier. L'analyse des profils salins des parcelles étudiées a montré une augmentation de la variabilité verticale (intra-profil) et spatiale (inter-profil) en relation avec les fréquences d'irrigation et les pratiques d'amendement du sable, la salinité et la profondeur de la nappe phréatique. La technique d'amendement du sable montre son efficacité dans la réduction de la salinité, à condition d'améliorer le réseau de drainage et de sensibiliser les agriculteurs à une meilleure gestion de l'irrigation selon les besoins en eau des cultures.

Mots-clés : Pratiques agricoles, oasis, eau d'irrigation, profils de salinité

ملخص

مشاكل إدارة مياه الري وملوحة التربة في واحة بالجنوب التونسي

تواجه الواحات والمناطق القاحلة في المغرب العربي تحديات رئيسية تتمثل في أنماط حوكمة موارد المياه، والتغيرات المناخية، وديناميات الأنظمة الزراعية. فيما يتعلق بالزراعات التجارية مثل التمر في الجنوب التونسي، يلجأ الفلاحون إلى استعمال كميات هامة من المياه بهدف زيادة الإنتاجية. وفي هذا السياق، أدى سوء إدارة مياه الري إلى ارتفاع مستوى المياه الجوفية مع تغدق مائي هدد استدامة النظام الواحي. من هنا، يهدف هذا البحث إلى دراسة مشاكل إدارة مياه الري وملوحة التربة في واحات النخيل في جنوب تونس. تم فحص الممارسات الزراعية من خلال استطلاعات وورش عمل تشاركية مع الفلاحين، بالإضافة إلى متابعة مستمرة لمحتوى الماء وملوحة التربة في الحقول الزراعية التي تستخدم نظام الري السطحي المحسن.

أظهرت النتائج استخداماً مكثفاً لمياه الري بسبب قلة معرفة الفلاحين بالاحتياجات المائية الضرورية لأشجار النخيل. كما كشف تحليل ملوحة التربة للمناطق المدروسة زيادة في التباين المقطعي العمودي والمكاني المتعلق بتواتر الري وتقنيات الردم و الملوحة وعمق المياه الجوفية. كما بينت نتائج البحث أهمية تقنية الردم في خفض ملوحة التربة، شريطة تحسين شبكة التصريف وتوعية الفلاحين بضرورة إدارة الري بشكل أفضل وفقاً لاحتياجات المحاصيل.

الكلمات المفتاحية : ممارسات زراعية، واحات، مياه الري، الملوحة

INTRODUCTION

The sustainability of irrigated agriculture, particularly in arid and semi-arid regions, is threatened by a combination of factors such as water quality, agricultural practices and salinization of groundwater and soils (Marlet et al., 2009). In Tunisia, the most affected areas by soil salinization are those that don't discharge the excess of water, such as the Medjerda Valley in the north and the oases in the south (Hachicha and Hallaire, 2002; Ferjani et al., 2013).

The scarcity of freshwater poses a significant challenge, resulting in continuous exploitation of deep low renewable groundwater (Besser et al., 2021; Dhaouadi et al., 2020; Hachicha and Ben Aissa, 2014), which is the only resource available to cover the irrigation needs of the oases. The exploitation of groundwater reservoirs ensures a consistent and permanent water supply during dry periods. Nevertheless, the persistent utilization of these

low-renewable, deep, and richly mineralized waters has the potential to negatively impact soil characteristics and agricultural yields.

Currently, oases fight with substantial challenges of waterlogging and salinization resulting from inadequate management of water and soil resources, along with reduced drainage water discharge. The equilibrium of oases relies on a delicate interplay among water, soil, and human activities. The traditional irrigation practices employed in the oasis system have led to various adverse effects on both soil fertility and the preservation of groundwater resources (Hamed, 2015; Haj-Amor et al., 2017).

Despite numerous investments in the agricultural water sector, irrigation as practiced in the oases, shows significant losses both in the tube-well, distribution and supply networks and in the farm network as well as in the agricultural plot (Al Atiri, 2005; Ghazouani, 2009; Dhaouadi et al., 2017). The mismanagement of water and soil resources based on a fragile balance between water, soil and man in the southern Tunisia oases, the abundant and irrational use of saline water for irrigation, water losses in earth channels and the lack of an effective drainage system have led to serious soil degradation problems in low-slope and low-lying areas, resulting in the rise of the aquifer (Van Ranst and Kadri, 2002).

Soil salinization generally results in degradation of the physical, chemical and biological properties of the soil and decreases in crop yields (Daoud and Halitim, 1994), hence there is a need to monitor soil salinity, determine the water and saline balance and assess the causes and sources of problems in order to choose management options to reduce soil resource degradation (Bouksila et al., 2013). Among these management options, several studies have shown that it is possible to use moderately salty water for irrigation without significant risk of soil salinization if certain water rules and soil management are respected (e.g., Legros, 2009; Bouksila et al., 2013).

According to Marlet and Job (2006), there is no single method of adaptation for farmers or a single way to control salinity, but a set of agronomic, hydraulic, managerial practices that can be combined according to circumstances. Installation of drainage systems to evacuate from the oasis, excess water and salts (Côte, 1988), periodic monitoring of groundwater and soil salinity trends (Hatira et al., 2005) and land amendments can mitigate the effects of degradation and in particular the decline in soil fertility in oases (Maatoug et al., 2019).

Over the past decades, problems of land fragmentation, hydromorphic and salinization have resulted in the low profitability of varieties that have the generic name “common dates” and the insufficient quantities of water allocated by the collective irrigation network have weakened the farms in the old oases (Ben Moussa et al., 2022 ; Mekki et al., 2021). This has led to a significant evolution of production systems currently based on date palm plantations (especially the Deglet Noor variety) and developed mostly outside the old oases in extensions irrigated from illicit tube-well (Mekki et al., 2021).

In 2020, the date palm production within these extension constituted approximately 85% of the total date production in the region and 81% of national date production (CRDA Kebili, 2020). Ghazouani (2009), revealed that farmers of the oasis of Fatnassa in Kebili are unable to identify certain causal relationships and that represents an alarming situation and a risk of degradation of resources (the relationship of waterlogging/salinity, saline stress/water stress, degradation of fertility and soil quality due to salinization and compaction, water stress and its effect on date palm, the degradation of fertility and soil quality and its effect on the date palm, ...).

Sustainable development strategies must focus on the agricultural and irrigation practices. In this context, this study addresses and discusses challenges related to irrigation water management and soil salinity control in date palm oases of Kebili located in southern Tunisia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Study Area

The governorate of Kebili is located in the southwest of Tunisia, it occupies an area of 22490 km². This region belongs mostly to the Saharan bioclimatic stage (annual average temperature of 20.9°C) with cold winter and hot summer. Annual rainfall is around 100 mm/year. Agricultural land accounts for 27% of the total area of Kebili governorate (621179 ha in 2018). The rangelands covering 83% of the useful agricultural area “UAA”(567070 ha) are located almost throughout the governorate. Oases cover 38000 ha (5% UAA), rainfed crops cover 26064 ha (4% UAA) and cropland cover 50000 ha (7% UAA). Forested areas cover 4109 ha, which represent 1% of the governorate’s UAA (CRDA, 2018). The soil texture in this area is a sandy to sandy-silty homogeneous texture with high gypsum content (CRDA 2015; Hachicha 2007).

The oases pump most of their water from deep aquifers from of the Northern Sahara Basin (SASS) and only to a small degree from shallow aquifers. The SASS known as the Continental Intercalary (CI), with a depth up to 3000 m in some areas and the Terminal Complex (CT), with a depth between 300 and 500 m, extend into the Tunisian Chotts region and the far south and extend beyond the country’s borders into Algeria (central basin) and Libya (El Hamada elHamra).

Farmers in the Kebili region embraced innovative ways to secure water, land, and energy resources. By the mid-1980s, cost-effective drilling techniques became readily accessible, leading to the establishment of unauthorized boreholes in newly extensions areas nearly of traditional oases. Diesel pumps were commonly employed by farmers for irrigation. In regions near urban areas, some farmers also resorted to use of electric pumps. Subsequently, starting from 2014, there was a shift towards the adoption of solar power, particularly in remote areas distant from urban centers. The rising adoption of solar panels for irrigation can be attributed to the escalating costs associated with fuel and electricity (Dhaouadi et al., 2021 ; Mekki et al., 2022). The present study concerns the M'outkhma extension of the ancient oasis of Om Somaasouth, which belongs to the Souk Lahad delegation (Fig. 1). The M'outkhma extensions are considered a continuation of ancient oases. Based on our digital cartography, We have approximated the total area of the extension within the Souk Lahad delegation to be around 4230 hectares, with 207 hectares located in Om Somaa south region. For most farmers, agriculture in this extension are family-run on a small scale. The date palm is the main crop with the exception of a few pomegranate and fig trees scattered over a few plots. These oases often border the edges of "chotts", depressions of saline soil that form natural outlets for drainage (Ben Aïssa et al., 2006).

Fig. 1. Location of study area.

2. Methods

The assessment of challenges regarding irrigation management and soil salinity focused on five plots situated in the extension of the Om Somaasouthern oasis (Fig. 2). This evaluation involved quantifying irrigation water allocations and analyzing saline profiles through a comparative study among these five plots, each employing different irrigation practices. Soil sampling was carried out on the diagonal of each plot (at the edges and in the middle; points P1, P2, P3, Fig.2), which are sometimes located within cultivated areas and other times near drains, starting from the top layer of the soil and going up to 100 cm (every 20 cm). Participatory interviews and workshops were used to analyse the factors explaining farmers' behaviour. This involves quantifying the supply of irrigation water and analysing the saline profiles of plots using different irrigation practices by (1) interviews with the five farmers who own these plots and (2) measurements of water consumption and soil salinity and soil moisture (drill & drop probes).

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of studied plots (p1, p2 , p3 are the sampling points)

A series of participatory workshops were organised between 2021 and 2022. The first two workshops, held in March 2021 with farmers and representatives of the water users' association (GDA Om Somâa Sud), were aimed at making a joint diagnosis of the situation. Cartographic tools (maps of the irrigation perimeter and the extensions of Om Somaa south) were used as supports for this discussion. A total of 19 farmers and 4 representatives of the Om Somaa Sud GDA took part in these workshops. A multi-actor workshop was organized on 22 May 2022, with local actors involved in the management of oases of Om Somaa south

(28 participants: farmers, water users association, CRDA Kébili, CTV OM Somâa sud) around irrigation and drainage management practices and their impacts on soil salinization. Interviews with farmers focused on (1) identifying the characteristics of the different plots (area, position...), (2) access to irrigation water (GDA collective network, private tube-well), (3) irrigation techniques (surface, drip, etc.), (4) the water management rules put in place by farmers (5) the drainage system (type of drain, size and depth of drains, drainage constraints).

A capacitive probe Drill and Drop Sentek have been installed in plot “1” since 2021. The probe measures a 60cm soil profile in 10cm slices. Soil moisture and soil temperature and soil salinity readings at each sensor, every 10cm down the soil profile. The measured data is transmitted in real time from the sensor to the Field Climate platform. For more accurate measurements, the soil texture was introduced into the platform. Depending on the soil type, saturation is between 37 and 40 %. The theoretical wilting point is positioned at 2/3 of the field capacity.

Fig. 3. Drill and Drop capacitive probes installed in Plot 1.

Soil analysis was conducted to determine soil salinity and water content at field capacity (θ_{cc}) and wilting point (θ_{pf}) at three points along the diagonal of each plot, spanning a depth of 100 cm in 20 cm intervals. This assessment was performed on January 20, 2022, across five plots. Subsequently, two additional sessions were carried out exclusively on plot 1: one on October 1, 2022, and another on March 10, 2023, following the resumption of irrigation after a mechanical breakdown of the tubewell. For each point (P_i) a soil profile on 1m was made to determine the electrical conductivity (CEe) in the laboratory using the 1/5 method and the saturated paste extract method. The analyses were carried out at the laboratory of the National Institute of Research in Rural Engineering, Water and Forests (INRGREF) and the Regional Commissary for Agricultural Development of Kebili (CRDA). Measurements of water content at field capacity (θ_{cc}) and wilt point (θ_{pf}) were made using the Richard.

The characteristics of the studied plots are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics studied plots

N° plot	Area (ha)	Access to water/ Type of pumping energy	Drainage system	Thickness of sand amendment (m)
1	0.37	Private/Diesel tube-well, Access to the GDA	No drain	0.5
2	0.47	Collective network irrigate only from private tube-well /solar energy	Open ditch (trapezoidal shape, depth 1.8 m)	0.5
3	0.17	Irrigate only from a diesel collective tube - well	Open ditch (trapezoidal shape, depth 1.8 m)	0.4
4	0.17	Irrigate only from a diesel collective tube - well	Open ditch (trapezoidal shape, depth 1.8 m)	0.4
5	1.4	Irrigate only from private tube-well /solar energy	Open ditch (trapezoidal shape, depth 1.8 m)	0.4

The volumes of water supplied were determined through the collection of water fees data received from the Om Somaasouth GDA. For individual boreholes, water flow measurements were carried out, combined with interviews with farmers, as well as a flow meter was installed at plot 1 to monitor the amounts of irrigation water, This plot is also irrigated from the GDA network.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Assessment of irrigation practices and soil moisture in the studied plots

The annual water requirement of palm trees for 2021/2022 season is computed to be 13775 m³/ha based on FAO°56 paper. Comparison of irrigation volumes provided by the five farmers to the water needs of the date palm during the month of March 2022 (Fig. 4) reveals that irrigations are not conducted according to the crops water requirements (based on FAO°56 paper) inducing over-irrigations especially for Plot2. In the case of plots 3 and 4, mechanical equipment installed on the boreholes experienced failures lasting for three months, resulting in a lack of irrigation during that period.

Fig. 4. Irrigation volumes and water requirement ($\text{m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{month}$) for the three plots.

We also noted a disruption in the irrigation of plot 1 from January 2022 to October 2022, caused by a mechanical malfunction in the private tube-well pump. Irrigation resumed at a frequency of four times per week, with an estimated supply of irrigation water at around $1330 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}.\text{month}$ (comprising water from the private tube-well and access from GDA). These irrigation volumes for this plot were confirmed by monitoring soil moisture using the drill and drop sensor (Fig. 5).

As expected, water content increased at each irrigation event, especially for layers near the surface, following peaks reaching 50% of volumetric water content “VWC” to decrease after than to 10 % of VWC according to root water uptake, water redistribution and evaporation until next irrigation event. We note that VWC in the top soil layers (10cm, 20cm and 30cm) is lower than the deep horizons (40cm, 50cm and 60cm). Intense peaks were more pronounced in the top soil layers (10–30 cm), close to the surface layer, due to irrigation volumes and soil crop atmosphere exchanges. Note that for the layers 50-60 cm, little variations of VWC can be observed after irrigation event.

Fig. 5. Soil water content monitoring in the plot1.

For plots 2 and 5, we record irrigation volumes of 4087 m³/ha.month and 2437.5 m³/ha.month respectively during the month of March with a frequency of irrigation every three days. Based on the computed crop water requirements of 938 m³/ha for the same month, it is concluded that both plots are over-irrigated.

2. Soil salinity variation

According to Duchaufour's textural triangle (1991), the soils of the studied plots exhibit a silty-sandy to silty texture with a higher proportion of sand due to soil amendments made to address the issues of salinization and hydromorphism. The pH value of these plots ranges between 8.06 and 8.23, indicating alkaline soil (according to Bocoum's classification, 2004).

The assessment of the effect of irrigation water management on soil salinity was conducted by analyzing salinity performed on January 20, 2022, across five plots. in relation to irrigation frequency, groundwater depth and salinity, as well as irrigation practices. The results of soil salinity profiles show high vertical (intraprofile) and spatial (inter-profile) variability in soil salinity. This is the case when the irrigation system, the sand amendments and the depth and salinity of the water table interact strongly with certain agricultural practices and strategies causing degradation of irrigated crop performance (Ghazouani et al., 2009). We observed the three types of saline profiles, similar to the saline profiles described by Servant (1975): descending, ascending and convex profiles.

The analysis of the saline profile of plot 1 indicates a decrease in salinity following the irrigation period, with a maximum value of approximately 3.13 ms/cm. However, there is evidence of salt accumulation at a depth of 80 cm, likely due to leaching. During the break period, salinity increases, particularly at a depth of 0.40 m, reaching an EC of 8 ms/cm before irrigation. a shallow of saline groundwater, coupled with insufficient leaching and drainage processes, contributes to the accumulation of salinity.

While irrigation helps reduce salinity to some extent, the absence of proper drainage exacerbates the issue, especially with irrigation water high in salinity (around 4 g/l). These factors compound the signs of hydromorphism, further disrupting the oasis system's salt balance.

Fig. 6. Salinity profiles (Plot 1), (irrigation frequency: 3 irrigation/ 10 days, amendment: 0.5 m, irrigation technique: improved submersion, private tube-well, , no, drainage

For plot 2, we observe a slight decrease in salinity within the layer (20-40 cm), followed by an increase in salinity within the layer (40-100 cm). The maximum salinity is found in the lower part of the profile (Fig.6). This distribution pattern is typical of soils with surface gypsum encrustation. Such a saline profile, described as descending by Servant (1975), suggests that the profile underwent a leaching phase of soluble salts. Salt accumulation was observed at a depth of approximately 80 cm from the soil surface. This phenomenon can be attributed to the leaching of salts and their migration through the irrigation water to deeper layers. Dissolved salts in irrigation water tend to accumulate in the soil due to evaporation and plant transpiration, leading to a gradual increase in soil solution concentration. The presence of a depression in the middle of plot 2 could also contribute to the elevated salinity in this area. Implementing soil amendments in this area would be beneficial in addressing the salinization issue within the plot.

Fig. 6. Salinity profiles (Plot 2), (irrigation frequency: 3 irrigation/ 10 days, amendment: 0.5 m, irrigation technique: improved submersion, private tube-well, solar energy pumping, existence of a low zone in the middle of a plot, drainage by an open ditch of depth of 1.8 m

The salinity profiles in plot 4 are shown in Fig. 7, this plot also shows an increase in salt which reached a value of about 5.7 ms/cm with an accumulation at a depth of about 80 cm of soil especially at point P1 which is near a drainage zone at the end of the plot. There is an increase in salinity especially at the P1 point, located at the end of the plot near a drainage zone. Generally, the increase in salinity in this plot is due to the lack of irrigation, following a mechanical failure of the collective tube-well also to the existence of a salty and shallow water table and the lack of leaching and sand amendment. This farmer decided to change the pumping technique and use solar energy instead of diesel engines that required maintenance.

Fig.7. Salinity profiles (Plot 4): (plot was not irrigated for a period of about three months due to a mechanical failure at the level of collective diesel well tube, amendment: 0.4 m, drainage by an open ditch depth of 1.8 m)

The saline profile of plot 5 is similar to the saline profile of plot 2; the salinity decreases slightly in the horizon (20-40 cm), then an increase in the horizon (40-100 cm) to reach a value of about 4,7 ms/cm (Fig. 8). This plot has a slightly higher salinity than plot 2. Soil sampling at the end and near Sebkhya may explain the increase in profile salinity P3.

Salinity profiles (plot 5)(Irrigation frequency: 4 irrigation/ month, amendment: 0.4 m, irrigation technique: improved submersion, private tube-well, solar energy pumping, drainage by an open ditch depth of 1.8 m)

3. Validation of results by participatory approach

Localisation of farmers plots, individual and collective wells were validated by participants during the diagnosis workshop. Characteristic of individual and collective drainage system were discussed and participants mapped the most affect zones by salinization (Fig. 9-a). During the multi-actor workshop, we presented the results of an analysis study of irrigation frequencies and doses and satisfaction level of water irrigation needs. We presented also the results of salinity analysis (soil and water) and we presented a map of the individual and collective drainage system (Fig. 9-b). Farmers confirmed the results of this analysis and explained that their practices depended on several factors such as the financial situation of the farmer and climatic variability. They identified the area of depression within the study areawhichexplains the high values of the measuredsalinity profiles in these plots. At the end of this workshop, participants discussed several practices to resist soil salinity mainly through the sand amendment technique and the maintenance of the drainage system.

Fig. 9.a-Participatory diagnosis of drainage problems in the oases of Om Somaa Sud (mars 2021); b-Multi-actor workshop conducted with local actors (mai 2022)

CONCLUSION

The objective of this study was to evaluate the impact of irrigation practices on soil salinity in southern Tunisian Oasis of OumSommâa. The results showed a significant vertical and spatial variation in soil salinity in relation to irrigation frequencies, soil amendment and groundwater depth. There have been excessive irrigations, which are mostly attributable to farmers' ignorance of the date palm's water requirements.

The improvement of the soils affected by the salinity of the southern oasis of OumSommâa is still possible, but depends on a minimal development to ensure a satisfactory depth of water. If the drainage system is upgraded and farmers are educated on how to effectively regulate irrigation water supply according to the needs of the crop, the sand amendment will prove effective in salinity control.

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